

A Comprehensive Study of Uterine Lesions in Hysterectomy Specimens: Clinical, Radiological, and Histopathological Insights

Sheetal Anil Ghugare¹, Lalita Yoganand Patil², Kusum Jashnani³¹Assistant Professor, Government Medical College, Buldhana²Professor, Topiwala National Medical College, Mumbai³Head of Department, Topiwala National Medical College, Mumbai

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Kusum Jashnani

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Abstract:

Introduction: Hysterectomy is a common surgical procedure performed worldwide to treat various benign and malignant uterine pathologies, including leiomyoma, adenomyosis, and endometrial abnormalities. This study aimed to evaluate the histopathological spectrum of uterine lesions in hysterectomy specimens and correlate clinical, radiological, and histopathological findings to determine the most common indications and pathological findings.

Methodology: This retrospective and prospective observational study analyzed 300 hysterectomy specimens collected between July 2017 and December 2018. The specimens were processed using routine paraffin tissue processing methods, and sections were stained with hematoxylin and eosin. Clinical data, including age, symptoms, and radiological findings, were correlated with histopathological results. Inclusion criteria included all hysterectomy specimens, while exclusion criteria ruled out cervical, ovarian, and fallopian tube lesions, as well as poorly preserved samples.

Results: The study found that the most common age group for hysterectomy was 41–50 years (43.00%). Menorrhagia (37.46%) and uterine prolapse (30.94%) were the most frequent clinical presentations. Histopathologically, the proliferative phase was the most common endometrial finding (37.46%), followed by atrophic endometrium (27.04%). Leiomyoma (43.32%) was the predominant myometrial lesion, with the intramural type (54.89%) and hyalinization (36.09%) as the most common subtype and secondary change, respectively. Adenomyosis (28.01%) was also frequently observed.

Conclusion: Hysterectomy is an effective treatment for various uterine pathologies, with leiomyoma and adenomyosis being the most common histopathological findings. The study highlights the significance of histopathological examination for accurate diagnosis and management, even in grossly normal specimens. Clinical and radiological evaluations alone may not adequately diagnose conditions such as adenomyosis or early-stage malignancies.

Keywords: Hysterectomy, leiomyoma, adenomyosis, histopathology, proliferative phase, uterine pathologies, clinical correlation.

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Introduction

Uterus, a vital reproductive organ is subjected to many benign and malignant disorders [4,10,12]. Most common clinical presenting features are per vaginal bleeding, vaginal discharge, and pain in abdomen, menstrual irregularity, and difficulty in micturition, postmenopausal bleeding and sensation of something coming out per vaginum [1].

Women worldwide suffer from gynecologic and obstetric disorders. Many treatment options are available including medical and conservative management but hysterectomy still remains the most common gynecological procedure performed worldwide [6,8,10,12]. Hysterectomy is the definitive treatment for many pelvic pathologies

which include leiomyoma, dysfunctional uterine bleeding, uterovaginal prolapse, endometriosis, adenomyosis, pelvic inflammatory disease, chronic pelvic pain, gynecological cancers and obstetric complications [3,7,9,10,11]. Histological examination of hysterectomy specimens carries diagnostic, therapeutic and prognostic significance [2,8].

Hysterectomy may be total/complete –removal of the body, fundus, and cervix of the uterus or partial /subtotal/ supracervical hysterectomy - removal of the uterine body while leaving the cervix intact. When along with total hysterectomy, unilateral/bilateral adnexae are removed it is called

as total hysterectomy with unilateral/ bilateral salpingoopherectomy(BSO)3 and when along with total hysterectomy unilateral/bilateral fallopian tubes are removed it is called as total hysterectomy with unilateral/bilateral salpingectomy.

Materials and Methods:

This is a retrospective and prospective observational study of one and half year duration from 1st July 2017 to 31st December 2018 during which 300 cases were studied. There clinical data (age, clinical presentation, radiologic findings and other available investigations), gross findings were obtained from the surgical histopathological record section of the institute. Inclusion criteria were all the hysterectomy specimen received in the surgical histopathology section and age distribution from 20 years to 80 years. Exclusion criteria were cervical lesions, ovarian lesions, fallopian tube lesions,

endometrial biopsy, cervical biopsy, myomectomy specimen, obstetric hysterectomy specimen, poor and unfixd specimen. In the retrospective period, formalin fixed paraffin embedded tissue sections stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) were retrieved and reviewed. In the prospective period, the hysterectomy specimens were received in 10% formalin in the surgical histopathology section and were studied by routine paraffin tissue processing method. 3-5 micron thick sections were made from paraffin embedded blocks and slides were stained with hematoxylin and eosin stain. All sections of uterus were examined for various pathologies.

Results:

In the present study, out of 307 hysterectomy cases, 56.35% (173 cases) had undergone total hysterectomy (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Types of hysterectomy

The commonest age group involved was 41-50 years (43.00%), mean age was 47.35 years and median age was 45 years (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Age-wise distribution

Multiparous - 91.53% (281 cases) were the commonest (Figure 3). Menorrhagia was the commonest presentation in 37.46% (115 cases), followed by something coming out per vagina in 30.94% (95 cases) (As shown in table 1).

Table 1: Distribution of Clinical Presentation:

Sr. No.	Clinical Presentation	No.	Percent (%)
1.	Menorrhagia	115	37.46 %
2.	Something coming out PV	95	30.94 %
3.	Lower abdominal pain	76	24.75 %
4.	Dysmenorrhea	48	15.64 %
5.	Polymenorrhagia	24	07.82 %
6.	Increased frequency of urination	20	06.51 %
7.	Vaginal discharge	19	06.19 %
8.	PV bleeding	19	06.19 %
9.	Postmenopausal bleeding	12	03.91 %
10.	Metrorrhagia	05	01.63%

The commonest histopathological findings of endometrium were proliferative phase in 37.46% (115 cases), followed by atrophic endometrium in 27.04% (83 cases) and of myometrium were Leiomyoma in 43.32% (133 cases), and followed by adenomyosis in 28.01% (86 cases) (Figure 4 &5 respectively).

Figure 3: Histopathological findings of endometrium

Figure 4: Histopathological findings of myometrium

The commonest age group involved in leiomyoma and adenomyosis was 41-50 years in 55.64% (74 cases) & 55.81% (48 cases) respectively (Table 2).

Table 2: Age-wise distribution of Leiomyoma & Adenomyosis:

Sr. No	Age group (years)	Leiomyoma (n =133)		Adenomyosis (n = 86)	
		No. of cases	Percent (%)	No. of cases	Percent (%)
1.	21-30	02	01.50%	02	02.32%
2.	31-40	33	24.81%	20	23.26%
3.	41-50	74	55.64%	48	55.81%
4.	51-60	19	14.29%	13	15.12%
5.	61-70	05	03.76%	03	03.49%
6.	71-80	00	00.00%	00	00.00%

Intramural was commonest site in 54.89% (73 cases) & hyalinization was the commonest secondary change in 36.09% (48 cases) of leiomyoma. The histological variant like cellular leiomyoma, neurilemmoma & lipoleiomyoma were seen. 69.77% (60 cases) of superficial adenomyosis were seen (Table 3).

Table 3) Leiomyoma - site wise distribution (n=133), Secondary changes & histological types of leiomyoma (n=133) and Adenomyosis with subtypes (n=86):

Sr. No	Leiomyoma with site wise distribution	No of cases	Percent (%)
1.	Subserosal	22	16.54 %
2.	Intramural	73	54.89 %
3.	Submucosal	09	06.77 %
4.	Subserosal+Intramural	21	15.79 %
5.	Subserosal+Submucosal	01	00.75 %
6.	Intramural+Submucosal	03	02.26 %
7.	Subserosal+Intramural+Submucosal	04	03.00 %
Sr. No.	Leiomyoma with/without secondary changes and histological variants	No of cases	Percent (%)
A	With secondary changes and histological variants	60	45.11 %
1.	Hyaline change	48	36.09 %
2.	Hyaline and myxoid change	01	00.75 %
3.	Hyaline change and calcification	01	00.75 %
4.	Hyaline change and red degeneration	01	00.75 %
5.	Hyaline change and neurilemmoma variant	02	01.50 %
6.	Cellular Leiomyoma	04	03.01 %
7.	Cellular leiomyoma with hyaline change and red degeneration	01	00.75 %
8.	Neurilemmoma variant of Leiomyoma	01	00.75 %
9.	Lipoleiomyoma	01	00.75 %
B	Without secondary changes and histological variants	73	54.89 %
Sr. No	Adenomyosis with subtypes	No. of cases	Percent(%)
1.	Superficial adenomyosis	60	69.77 %
2.	Superficial and deep adenomyosis	26	30.23 %

The association of radio histopathological examination findings of uterine fibroid were seen in 98 cases, of endometrial polyp seen in 3 cases and for adenomyosis were seen in 9 cases (Table 4).

Table 4) Comparison of USG findings of uterine fibroid, endometrial polyp and adenomyosis with histopathological findings:

On Ultrasonography	Histopathological findings			P value
Uterine fibroid	Present	Absent	Total	< 0.05 Significant
Present	98	26	124	
Absent	35	148	183	
Total	133	174	307	
Endometrial polyp	Present	Absent	Total	
Present	03	02	05	
Absent	31	271	302	
Total	34	273	307	

Adenomyosis	Present	Absent	Total
Present	09	03	12
Absent	77	218	295
Total	86	221	307

Discussion

In the present study, the commonest age group involved was 41-50 years in 43.00% cases, which is in concordance with study of Ticku et al [3] study (41.76%) and is comparable with Maheshwari J et al [2] (50.22%), Kaur et al [7] studies (51.00%) but it shows higher percentage in their studies.

Second most common age group involved was 31-40 years in 25.40% cases, which is in concordance with Maheshwari J et al [2] (25.11%), Kaur et al [7] studies (25.50%). Menorrhagia was the commonest clinical presentation in 37.46%, followed by something coming out per vaginum in 30.94% and vaginal discharge in 06.19% which are in concordance with Kaur et al [7] study. i.e. (38.00%, 29.00% and 06.50% respectively).

Proliferative phase was the commonest endometrial histopathological finding in 37.46% cases, which is in concordance with Ticku et al ([3] (38.36%), Kaur et al [7] (31.00%) studies and is in discordance with Fatehpuriya DS et al [4], Verma D et al [11] studies (83.90% & 53.00% respectively) due to high percentage of endometrial lesions but the commonest endometrial histopathological findings in their studies is proliferative phase of endometrium.

The second most common endometrial finding was atrophic endometrium in 27.04% cases, which is comparable with Gangadharan V et al [5] study (24.50%). Other endometrial findings were secretory phase in 14.33% cases, which is in concordance with Kaur et al [7] study. i.e.(13.00%). Acute endometritis and chronic endometritis were seen in 00.33% and 1.30% cases respectively, which are in concordance with Ticku et al [3] (00.25% & 1.48% respectively). Endometrial adenocarcinoma was seen in 00.65% cases, which is in concordance with Gangadharan V et al [5] study. i.e. (00.60%).

Leiomyoma was the commonest myometrial histopathological finding in 43.32% cases, which is in concordance with Tiwana KK et al [9] (43.70%), Maheshwari J et al [2] (42.30%), Gangadharan V et al [5] (41.00%) studies. It is in discordance with Gattu V et al [6] (60.00%), Fatehpuriya DS et al [4] (58.80%), Kaur et al [7] (65.00%) studies due to higher percentage and with Verma D et al [11] (25.60%) study due to lower percentage of Leiomyoma. Intramural location of leiomyoma was the commonest finding in 54.89% which is comparable with Kaur et al [7] study i.e.(62.90%).

Lipoleiomyoma was seen in 00.75% which is in concordance with Gattu V et al [6] study. i.e (00.50%). The most common secondary change noted was hyalinization in 36.09%, which is comparable with Kaur et al [7] study i.e. (33.30%). Leiomyoma and adenomyosis were commonly seen in the age group of 41-50 years in 55.64% and 55.81% cases respectively, which are comparable with Ticku et al [3] study i.e.(49.64% & 46.58%). In the present study, p-value is significant for histopathological examination of leiomyoma, endometrial polyp and adenomyosis than radiological examination. The laboratory investigations were analyzed in all the hysterectomy cases and were within normal limits.

Conclusion

Hysterectomy remains the widely used treatment modality for various uterine pathologies. The present study was undertaken to evaluate the various histopathological spectrum of uterine lesions, their commonest age group distribution, clinical and radiological features. A clinicopathological correlation is necessary for proper interpretation of the diagnosis.

This was done in our study, where clinical findings were correlated with the histopathological findings. Clinical history including age, presentation, radiological findings, laboratory investigations, gross examinations and microscopic examinations were properly studied. The commonest histopathological finding in endometrium is proliferative phase and leiomyoma in myometrium with the commonest site being Intramural.

The most common age group is 41-50 years in which hysterectomy were done. Menorrhagia was the commonest clinical presentation. The most common indication for hysterectomy in our setting is excessive uterine bleeding. Leiomyoma was the most common histopathological finding for which hysterectomy was performed. Clinical examination and radiological evaluation may diagnose the fibroid uterus, polyps, prolapsed uterus and related complications. But abnormal excessive uterine bleeding due adenomyosis, endometritis, hyperplasia, early stages of malignant uterine lesions are quite difficult to diagnose clinicoradiologically and were confirmed by histopathological examination.

Hence, it is mandatory that every hysterectomy specimen, even if it is grossly appears to be normal, should be subjected to detailed histopathological examination. So histopathological examination is

mandatory for confirming the diagnosis and thus ensuring the proper management.

References

1. Baral R, Sherpa P, Gautam D. Histopathological analysis of hysterectomy specimens: one year study. *Journal of Pathology of Nepal*. 2017; 7(1):1084-6.
2. Dr. J. Maheswari "Histopathological Spectrum of Lesions in Hysterectomy Specimens at A Tertiary Care Hospital- One Year Study." *IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences (IOSRJDMS)*, vol. 16, no. 10, 2017, pp. 34-38.
3. Dr. Singh P, Dr. Ticku A and Dr. Jamwal G. Histopathological Spectrum of Hysterectomy Specimens In Tertiary Care Hospital: A Prospective Study. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical sciences*, 2017, Volume 4, Issue 8, 858-866.
4. Fatehpuriya DS, Verma L, Sharma S. Clinico-pathological study of hysterectomy in benign lesions: a study of 379 hysterectomies. *Int J Reprod Contracept ObstetGynecol*2017; 6:934-8.
5. Gangadharan V &Prasanthi C. Hysterectomy - a clinico-pathological correlation in a rural setting. *Indian Journal of Basic and Applied Medical Research*. 2016. 5(2), 8-15.
6. Gattu V, Vellanki S, Reddy RM, Sekhar C. Histomorphological study of uterus and cervix and correlation with clinical diagnosis. *Sch J. App. Med. Sci*. 2016; 4:4285-90.
7. Kaur SJ, Gupta RK, Kaur M. Clinicopathological Study of Uterine Lesions in Hysterectomy Specimens. *Ann. Int. Med. Den. Res*. 2018; 4(1): PT18-PT22.
8. Rather GR, Gupta Y, Bardhwaj S. Patterns of lesions in hysterectomy specimens: a prospective study. *JK science*. 2013; 15(2):63-68.
9. Tiwana KK, Nibhoria S, Monga T, Phutela R. Histopathological audit of 373 nononcological hysterectomies in a teaching hospital. *Pathology research international*. 2014; 1-5.
10. Vaidya S, Vaidya SA. Patterns of Lesions in Hysterectomy Specimens in a Tertiary Care Hospital. *Journal of the Nepal Medical Association*. 2015; 53(197):18-23.
11. Verma D, Singh P, Kulshrestha R. Analysis of histopathological examination of the hysterectomy specimens in a north Indian teaching institute. *International Journal of Research in Medical Sciences*. 2016; 4(11):4753-8.
12. Zaid SMO, Thabet B, Abood M. Histopathological findings in hysterectomy specimens: A retrospective study. *Middle East Journal of Internal Medicine*. 2017. Volume 10, Issue 1:17-24.